

The Scientific Impact of ACCESS

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The Advanced Cyberinfrastructure Coordination Ecosystem: Services & Support (ACCESS) program was launched by the National Science Foundation (NSF) in 2022 as the latest evolution of the NSF's 40-year-old support for a national-scale cyberinfrastructure ecosystem. The transition to ACCESS included a significant transformation in the policies and processes for obtaining resource allocations. While the largest allocations of resource time still require substantial proposal effort and close review, the vast majority of researchers are able to access resources quickly and with significantly less proposal effort and proportionally less effort for ACCESS allocations staff and volunteer reviewers. Due in large part to these changes, the first three years of ACCESS have realized a twofold increase in the number of projects and principal investigators along with a threefold increase in the number of jobs run. The end result has been to substantially broaden use as well as minimize the "time to science" for researchers. Overall, the policy changes, combined with increased resource capacity available from ACCESS-allocated resources, supported a transition from allocations as "gatekeeper" mode to a more welcoming "gateway" approach and have dramatically changed the impact of the ACCESS ecosystem on the research and education community.

CCS Concepts: • **General and reference** → **Metrics; Empirical studies**; • **Social and professional topics** → *Management of computing and information systems*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: ACCESS, XDMoD, Allocations Process, Metrics, High-performance Computing

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1 Introduction

The Advanced Cyberinfrastructure Coordination Ecosystem: Services & Support (ACCESS) program [1] was launched by the National Science Foundation (NSF) in 2022 as the latest decadal evolution of the NSF's 40-year-old support for a national-scale cyberinfrastructure ecosystem. That transition included a significant transformation in the policies and processes for resource allocations, intended to accomplish one of the overarching goals for the ACCESS program, namely to enable broad access to these resources through reduced barriers to access.

The allocations process is the gateway to using resources that are part of the NSF's national cyberinfrastructure ecosystem. ACCESS does not operate advanced computing resources but rather allocates computing resources supported primarily through other independent NSF awards. Although researchers and educators are not charged to use ACCESS-allocated resources, ACCESS requires all users to provide information about the nature of the work to be conducted on

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ACCESS resources. Upon confirmation of eligibility and completion of the review process, ACCESS makes allocation awards to projects that define the researcher’s or educator’s ability to use resources.

Because the ACCESS awardees have retained allocations and usage data for at least two earlier NSF cyberinfrastructure programs, we are able to demonstrate the impact of these policy changes compared to the years prior to ACCESS, during the Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment (XSEDE) project [7]. The bulk of this paper focuses on metrics of allocations and resource activity over the past five years—the last two years of XSEDE and the first three years of ACCESS. Further data is available from XSEDE’s published reports [6] and the ACCESS Allocations Service annual reports [3]. The data is also accessible via the ACCESS Metrics Service instance of XDMoD [2].

Scientific impact can be measured in many ways, here we measure it in terms of metrics centered on access and usage, including facilitating access for researchers with smaller scale computing requirements. In the following sections, we first look at the changes seen in the volume and characteristics of incoming allocations requests. Then, we explore the impacts that the changes to allocations have had on the ACCESS user community and resource usage. Finally, we conclude with a brief discussion on the community and scientific outcomes more generally.

2 Allocations

The allocation policies implemented under ACCESS introduced two key changes in an effort to offer an efficient, scalable, and simplified request and review framework that would reduce real and perceived barriers in connecting researchers to resources. First, the ACCESS policies established four types of projects of increasing scale and proposal effort; the key features of the project types are summarized in Table 1. In contrast, the prior XSEDE program had two primary project types [9]. In most cases, researchers had the option of either Startup or Research project types—with Startup options limited to very modest allocation amounts and made for one year—and virtually all researchers were expected to eventually prepare Research project proposals, which entailed 10-page proposal documents, multiple supporting documents, and a quarterly panel review cycle [10]. By comparison, the smallest ACCESS project type, Explore, offers roughly eight times the amount of resources as an XSEDE Startup project. Figure 1 shows the impact of these policy changes on the number of projects awarded per year, with the ACCESS program policies fully implemented in 2023. Indeed, since the start of ACCESS, there has been a twofold increase in both open projects and the number of unique principal investigators (PIs), emphasizing that the project growth was not solely due to ACCESS policy changes that permitted researchers to have more than one project in certain cases.

The second major policy change was to allow graduate students to serve as PIs on allocated projects. Figure 1 also highlights the impact of allowing graduate students to request and lead their own projects. Graduate students have long been the largest group of users on allocated projects, but they had limited opportunities to lead projects and typically would fit their work within their advisor’s project. The response by graduate students to this new policy has been remarkable, with over 1,400 graduate students serving as project PIs in 2025, compared to around 50 during the final years of XSEDE. It is important to note that the overall project growth is not due solely to graduate student led projects; the number of projects led by non-graduate students also nearly doubled, demonstrating that these policies benefited all types of PIs.

Key to the ACCESS Allocations goal of broadening access was the introduction of the Explore and Discover project types, which allow new users to begin running on the available systems without an onerous application process. For example, in the case of Explore projects, access is obtained through a short web-based form without a lengthy proposal. The objective of the project types was to provide entry points into ACCESS that aligned with the well known “long tail” distribution of project resource usage that showed many research projects only needed smaller allocations to

Fig. 1. Growth in the number of projects awarded by calendar year broken down by the PI's academic status. The transition from XSEDE to ACCESS was in September 2022.

Fig. 2. Growth in the number of projects with awarded allocations by allocation type since calendar year 2020. Calendar year 2023 was the first full year of ACCESS.

Table 1. ACCESS Allocation Types

Allocation Type	Max award (ACCESS Credits)	Requests accepted	Required justification	Grad. Student PIs allowed
Explore	400,000	Anytime	Overview	Yes
Discover	1,500,000	Anytime	1-page proposal	Yes
Accelerate	3,000,000	Anytime	3-page proposal (max)	No
Maximize	Awarded by review	Every 6 months	10-page proposal (max)	No

accomplish their research objectives [4]. Figure 2 shows the distribution of the four different ACCESS project types over time. Consistent with the expected distribution of resource use, most allocation request activity happens among the smaller-scale Explore and Discover projects. The figure also shows the transition from the roughly even split of Startup and Research projects during XSEDE to mostly Explore and Discover type projects during ACCESS.

ACCESS policies and procedures have also allowed most allocation requests to be successful, with a success rate greater than 90% for all three years [3]. In contrast, XSEDE achieved a success rate approaching 85% by the end of the program after seeing success rates for Research proposals dip as low as 65% [5]. Furthermore, XSEDE generally took longer to process allocation proposals, with the Research proposal cycle taking 2.5 months from submission deadline to allocation award, and the time to make a Startup allocation decreasing gradually to about seven days later in the program [8]. In contrast, the typical ACCESS project has an award decision within one day and is able to go from proposal submission to completing its first resource job in less than 10 days [3], achieving a welcome decrease in “time to science” for researchers.

We also considered whether the external landscape of science had an effect on project growth, particularly whether the growth of interest in artificial intelligence (AI) has contributed to the growth in the number of projects. Figure 3, which is a plot of the number of projects broken out by field of science, shows that ACCESS has been supporting a rapidly growing number of computer science- and AI-related projects, with the number of computer science and AI-related projects growing 10-fold. However, even assuming some AI-related activity in projects associated with other domains, the number of projects in other domains has still doubled from ~2,800 in 2022 (the last year of XSEDE) to ~5,200 in 2025. With ~2,200 computer science- and AI-related projects awarded in 2024 and 2025, ACCESS is successfully serving the research community's need for high-performance computing for AI research.

Fig. 3. The number of projects by field of science over time. Projects in computer science and AI have grown significantly since 2021 through 2025.

Fig. 4. The number of people with user accounts, number of people using compute, and number of new people getting accounts on ACCESS-allocated resources by year.

3 Ecosystem Activity and Usage

While the policy changes clearly impacted the number of allocation requests and awards, the existence of projects does not automatically guarantee that actual resource usage saw comparable changes. In this section we provide a variety of metrics that address the growth in usage under the ACCESS program with particular focus on how access has been broadened across the research community. *To help provide a context for this discussion as well as provide an indication of the magnitude of the usage that ACCESS supports, we note that in a given month, more than 2.5 million jobs are run on average by more than 4,000 researchers representing more than 2,000 unique research projects.*

Figure 4 shows the growth in the number of users engaging with ACCESS-allocated resources. Since 2021, the number of open accounts each year (users potentially able to run jobs on resources) and the number of new users (those making their first appearance on ACCESS-allocated resources) have grown by 50%, and the number of active users (users actually charging jobs) each year has nearly doubled during the ACCESS period. In contrast, over the final five years of XSEDE the user counts remained stable with ~19,000 users with accounts and ~9,000 users active on resources each year, each of which is about half of the ACCESS totals for 2025.

Along with more users, ACCESS has seen steady growth in usage over time as shown in Figure 5. Here we show growth both in terms of the number of jobs run and consumed ACCESS Credit Equivalents (ACEs), which is a normalized unit of computing that accounts for the differences in processor performance. The number of jobs and the amount of ACEs used have more than doubled from 2021 to 2025. The mean job size has stayed approximately constant throughout so the growth rate of jobs and ACEs closely match. The compute resources that are allocated via ACCESS (and XSEDE) run at full capacity, so the plot of usage in ACEs closely match the ACEs available. For example, the step increase in ACEs used in Q2 2024 is due to the introduction of Stampede3 at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) and the increase in Q1 2025 is due to the Delta AI resource at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA).

Figure 6 shows the growth in usage in terms of ACEs broken out by the four ACCESS allocation types along with XSEDE's Research and Startup projects prior to and during the transition to ACCESS. Not surprisingly, the design of the ACCESS allocations policies ensures that the majority of usage is from the closely reviewed, large-scale Maximize projects. However, the steady growth in usage by Discover and Explore allocations shows how well received these allocations were by the research community due to their simpler application process and quicker turnaround time. Usage by Discover projects is outpacing Accelerate projects mainly because Discover projects outnumber Accelerate by

Fig. 5. Overall growth in ACCESS usage over time in terms of number of jobs run (blue bars) and ACCESS Credit Equivalents (red line).

Fig. 6. Usage by allocation type. Research type projects typically accounted for 95% or more of reported usage during the XSEDE program.

five to one; on a per-project basis, Accelerate projects are far more likely to consume their allocations. If we consider the number of jobs run (not shown in the figure) as opposed to usage, then the growth in the Discover and Explore allocations is even more striking. *Indeed, in 2025 there were more jobs run by Discover and Explore projects (14 million) than by Maximize projects (12.5 million).* This result was not unexpected, and providing these opportunities for smaller-scale projects was a primary driver in developing the new allocation policies of ACCESS. It is worth noting that currently 25% of reported publications are from Discover and Explore projects, providing evidence of the important role they play in the scientific ecosystem.

While growing usage given the increasing number of projects would perhaps be expected, we also looked at how successful projects of each type were at making use of resources. Figure 7 shows the percentage of projects of each type that reported some usage in a given year. The proportion of projects that had usage appears to be correlated with the amount of effort required to apply for the project (see Table 1). Almost all Maximize ACCESS projects are making use of their allocations, while XSEDE Research projects used allocations at roughly the same rate as Accelerate ACCESS projects, just over 80%. About 70% of Discover projects use their allocations, while only about 50% of Explore projects have usage—which is about the same rate as XSEDE Startup and Educational projects. The proportion of projects that have usage does not vary significantly year to year except for the XSEDE to ACCESS transition year 2022.

Finally, Figure 8 shows usage over time by different fields of science. The figure shows that usage by computer and information science projects (which includes AI) has grown considerably—from 55 million ACEs in 2021 to 471 million ACEs in 2025—but overall usage is still dominated by projects in physical sciences, engineering and technology, and biological sciences, which comprised 70% of all usage in 2025.

4 Conclusion

The transition from XSEDE to ACCESS has provided a unique opportunity to examine the impact that allocation policies can have on the interest and use of national-scale cyberinfrastructure resources. Under XSEDE, the number of proposals and projects each year remained largely flat, reflecting that the allocation policies may have unintentionally served a “gatekeeper” role ensuring that only the researchers who were most determined and most skilled in preparing allocation proposals were granted access to resources. In contrast, the allocation policies implemented under ACCESS have served as a more welcoming gateway and as a result have significantly broadened access by the research community, especially those needing only smaller allocations to accomplish their research, as evidenced by a twofold increase in the number of projects and PIs in the first three years of ACCESS. In addition, in 2025 more than 25% of the scientific publications reported were from Explore and Discover projects, providing evidence of the scientific impact of the allocation changes.

Fig. 7. Percent of open projects of each type recording some use of resources in a given year.

The emergence of AI-related activities as a significant source of allocation requests and resource usage does perhaps qualify these conclusions somewhat. The changing AI landscape has certainly been a large driver for allocations and usage during ACCESS, complementing the AI-focused NAIRR Pilot opportunities. Nonetheless, the ACCESS policies and procedures have been able to meet the AI-driven demand and maintain the goals of efficient proposal review and processing for most projects and support a community of researchers and educators that had previously not leveraged these national-scale resources.

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Fig. 8. Compute usage in ACCESS Credit Equivalents by the parent field of science each year.